

Clinical and Epidemiological Profile of Vulvar Lesions in a Tertiary Care Hospital in Mexico: An Overview of Malignant and Premalignant Lesions

García-Gutiérrez Mariana¹, Limón- Toledo Laura Patricia², Zavalza-Gómez Ana Bertha³

¹Fourth-year Resident in Gynecology and Obstetrics, Mexican Institute of Social Security, High Specialty Medical Unit, Gynecology-Obstetrics Hospital, Western National Medical Center, Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico.

²Obstetrician-Gynecologist, Mexican Institute of Social Security, High Specialty Medical Unit, Gynecology-Obstetrics Hospital, Western National Medical Center, Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico.

³Head of the Division of Health Research, Mexican Institute of Social Security, High Specialty Medical Unit, Gynecology-Obstetrics Hospital, Western National Medical Center, Guadalajara, Jalisco, Mexico.

ABSTRACT

Background: In recent years, various authors have reported an increase in vulvar cancer incidence, often preceded by premalignant vulvar lesions, which are now affecting younger women with concurrent factors such as smoking, immunosuppressive states (e.g., HIV), and post-transplant conditions. These premalignant lesions are defined as physical and biochemical factors that affect the vulvar epithelium and may progress to malignancy if not diagnosed and treated promptly. While vulvar cancer incidence rises with age, the average age has recently decreased, particularly among women aged 45 to 60. The GLOBOCAN database reported a prevalence of vulvar cancer in Central America at 2.02/100,000 persons, with 1166 cases in Mexico over five years. However, current clinical-epidemiological data from the Mexican population are lacking.

Materials and Methods: This descriptive, retrospective, and cross-sectional study was conducted at the High Specialty Medical Unit of the Gynaecology-Obstetrics Hospital, National Medical Center of the West (UMAЕ HGO CMNO), where data were collected from 156 patient files in the dysplasia clinic. Clinical and sociodemographic data such as age, marital status, education level, smoking history, sexual orientation, comorbidities, physical examination findings, and biopsy results were analyzed using SPSS v.23 and Excel databases. The study was approved by the ethics committee of UMAЕ HGO CMNO, with no risks to patients due to the descriptive and retrospective nature of the study.

Results: The study included 156 patients who met the inclusion criteria, with clinical and sociodemographic data collected from electronic and physical patient records. Various types of vulvar lesions were identified, categorized into four groups: benign, malignant or vulvar intraepithelial neoplasias (VIN), infectious, and inflammatory. Malignant lesions, particularly VIN, represented the most common etiology, accounting for 41% of the total sample. The majority of patients (62.12%) were between 19 and 50 years old, with a mean age of 38.57 years. The most common comorbidities were hypertension (23.44%), diabetes (17.19%), and immunological diseases (12.50%). The presence of HPV in the cervix was found in 26.56% of cases.

Discussion: The aim of this study was to establish a clinical-epidemiological profile of patients with vulvar lesions in our region, providing insight into the frequency and characteristics of such lesions. This is particularly relevant as there is limited literature in Mexico addressing risk factors and clinical manifestations of vulvar lesions. Our findings align with international studies reporting an increase in vulvar cancer, primarily linked to HPV infection, immunosuppressive states, and smoking. The most frequent age group in our study was women in their fertile years, similar to reports from other Latin American countries. Despite the known association with HPV, our study highlighted a low use of barrier methods among patients.

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Conclusions: Vulvar pathology remains under-studied in Mexico, despite a growing incidence of vulvar cancer globally, often stemming from precursor lesions like VIN, which are mostly linked to HPV. This study's findings reflect a similar epidemiology to international reports. Given the association with HPV, it is crucial to implement targeted screening and awareness strategies for the timely detection and treatment of premalignant lesions. This will improve the management of vulvar pathology and help healthcare professionals address this issue in our population effectively.

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KEYWORDS : Risk factors, vulvar cancer, epidemiology, pre-invasive vulvar lesions.

BACKGROUND

In recent years, several studies have reported an increase in the incidence of vulvar cancer, preceded by premalignant vulvar lesions. These conditions are increasingly associated with younger women and concurrent factors such as smoking and immunosuppressive states, including human immunodeficiency virus (HIV) infection and post-transplant immunosuppression (1). Premalignant vulvar lesions are defined as physical and biochemical factors that affect the vulvar epithelium and may progress to malignancy in the absence of timely diagnosis and treatment (2).

The incidence of vulvar cancer increases with age, with a global median age of 68 years. However, a decrease in the average age has been observed in recent years, now affecting women between 45 and 60 years (3). According to GLOBOCAN 2020, the 5-year prevalence of vulvar cancer in Central America is 2.02 per 100,000 people, with 1,166 cases reported in Mexico over a five-year period (4). However, current epidemiological and clinical data on vulvar cancer in the Mexican population remains scarce.

METHODOLOGY

A retrospective cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted at the High Specialty Medical Unit, Gynecology and Obstetrics Hospital, Western National Medical Center

(UMAE HGO CMNO). Information was collected from 156 electronic and physical patient records from the dysplasia clinic, including demographic data (age, marital status, education level, smoking status, sexual orientation, comorbidities), physical examination findings, and biopsy results. Data analysis was performed using SPSS v.23 and an Excel database.

The study was approved by the Ethics and Research Committee of UMAE HGO CMNO and posed no risk to patients due to its descriptive and retrospective nature.

RESULTS

A total of 156 patient records meeting inclusion criteria were analyzed. Clinical and sociodemographic data were obtained from both electronic and physical medical records of patients treated at the UMAE HGO CMNO dysplasia clinic.

Vulvar lesions were classified into four categories:

1. Benign
2. Malignant or vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia (VIN)
3. Infectious
4. Inflammatory

Malignant lesions and precursor lesions (VIN) represented the most significant and frequent category, accounting for 41% of the total sample.

Percentage of malignant lesions and intraepithelial neoplasias of the vulva

Graph 1. Percentage of malignant lesions and intraepithelial neoplasias of the vulva.

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Among VIN cases, the majority (47.8%) were classified as VIN I, 4.2% as VIN II, and 17.4% as VIN III. Squamous cell carcinoma accounted for 30.4% of cases.

Figure 1. Percentage and frequency of vulvar lesion etiology.

Sociodemographic Data

In Table 1 describes the most important sociodemographic data of the patients in our hospital, where the following data are observed.

- Age: Most patients (62.12%) were of reproductive age (19-50 years), with a mean age of 38.57 years. Only 33.33% were over 50 years old.
- Education: Basic education was the most frequent (66.67%), while 15.15% had completed secondary education, and 15.15% had higher education.
- Marital Status: Married women represented the highest percentage (57.58%), followed by single women (13.64%), cohabiting (12.12%), and widowed (10.67%).
- Smoking Status: 24.24% of patients reported being smokers.
- Sexual Orientation: 93.94% identified as heterosexual, while 6.06% identified as homosexual.
- Occupation: The majority were employed (46.97%), followed by housewives (43.94%).

Table 1. Frequencies and percentages of sociodemographic factors of patients with intraepithelial neoplasia and vulvar cancer

Socio-demographic background		
	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
• < 18	1	1.52%
• 19-50	41	62.12%
• >50	22	33.33%
Education		
• Basic	44	66.67%
• Secondary education	10	15.15%
• Higher education	10	15.15%
Marital Status		
• Single	9	13.64%
• Cohabiting	8	12.12%
• Married	38	57.58%
• Widow	7	10.61%
Smoking Status		
• Positive	16	24.24%
• Negative	48	72.73%
Sexual orientation		
• Heterosexual	62	93.94%
• Homosexual	4	6.06%

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Occupation		
• Housewives	29	43.94%
• Employed	31	46.97%
• Retired	4	6.06%

Comorbidities

The main comorbidities identified in patients with malignant and premalignant lesions of the vulva were arterial hypertension (23.44%), diabetes (17.19%) and immunological diseases (12.50%). In addition, coexistence of human papillomavirus infection in the cervix was observed in 17 patients, which represents 26.56% of the cases. Likewise,

coexistence with condylomatosis occurred in 20.31% and only one patient (1.56%) had human immunodeficiency virus infection. Other comorbidities presented included hypothyroidism (10.94%), chronic kidney disease (9.38%), history of kidney transplant (3.13%), and anxiety and depression disorders (4.69%). Likewise, it can be seen that 16.7% had use of immunosuppressants. (Table 2, Graph 2)

Table 2. Comorbidities found in patients with malignant vulvar lesions and intraepithelial neoplasias of the vulva

Comorbidities		
	Frequency	Percentage
Diabetes	11	17.19%
Hypertension	15	23.44%
Hypothyroidism	7	10.94%
Chronic Kidney Disease	6	9.38%
Immunological Diseases	8	12.50%
Cancer		
• Cervical cancer	7	10.94%
• Breast cancer	5	7.81%
• Endometrial cancer	1	1.56%
• Vaginal cancer	5	7.81%
kidney transplant	2	3.13%
Heart disease	2	3.13%
Infectious diseases		
• HIV	1	1.56%
• HPV Co-Infection	17	26.56%
• Condylomatosis	13	20.31%
Anxiety and Depression	3	4.69%
Body mass index		
• <18.5	4	6.25%
• 18.5-24.9	19	29.69%
• 25-29.9	16	25%
• 30-34.9	16	25%
• 35-39.9	6	9.38%
• >40	3	4.69%

Use of immunosuppressants

Graph 2. Percentage of use of immunosuppressants in patients with malignant lesions and intraepithelial neoplasia of the vulva.

Gynecological and Obstetric History

With respect to the gynecologic history of patients with vulvar cancer or intraepithelial lesions, the findings were as follows: menarche occurred at the expected age in 63 patients (98.44%). The majority (54.69%) initiated sexual activity before the age of 18, and 48.44% reported having only one sexual partner. A significant percentage (76.56%) did not use

any contraceptive method, with bilateral tubal ligation being the most commonly used method (12.50%), while only 1.56% reported using a barrier method. At the time of diagnosis, 5 patients (7.81%) were pregnant. Regarding menopause, the highest percentage (28.13%) occurred at the expected age (Table 3).

Table 3. Gynecologic-Obstetric History

Gynecologic-Obstetric History		
	Frequency	Percentage
Menarche		
• Early	0	-
• Normal	63	98.44%
• Late	1	1.56%
Menopause		
• Early	2	3.13%
• Normal	18	28.13%
• Not aplicable/ not reported	44	68.75%
Sexual initiation		
• < 18 years	35	54.69%
• >18 years	29	45.31%
Number of sexual partners		
• 1	31	48.44%
• 2 a 5	27	42.19%
• > a 5	8	12.50%
Contraceptive use		
• None	49	76.56%
• Condom	1	1.56%

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• Birth control pills	0	-
• Intrauterine device (IUD)	2	3.13%
• Hormonal IUD	0	-
• Hormonal Implant	2	3.13%
• Tubal Ligation	8	12.50%
Pregnancy at diagnosis	5	7.81%

Clinical Characteristics of Vulvar Lesions

The clinical characteristics of patients with vulvar lesions treated at our hospital unit are presented in **Table 4**. The most relevant findings were as follows:

- **Anatomical location:** The most commonly affected areas were the labia minora (59.38%) and the labia majora (34.38%).
- **Morphology:** The predominant lesion types were verrucous lesions (42.19%) and acetowhite-reactive lesions (25%).

- **Coloration:** Most lesions had a normal skin appearance (60.94%), followed by hyperpigmentation in 28.13% of cases.
- **Symptomatology:** A total of 49 patients (76.56%) were asymptomatic. However, the most frequently reported symptom was pruritus, present in 9 women (14%).

Table 4. Table 6. Clinical characteristics of malignant and premalignant vulvar lesions.

Clinical Characteristics of Vulvar Lesions		
	Frequency	Percentage
Anatomical Location		
• Inguinal region	1	1.56%
• Mons pubis	11	17.19%
• Labia majora	22	34.38%
• Labia minora	38	59.38%
• Vaginal Introitus	11	17.19%
• Perineum	15	23.44%
• Perianal region	6	9.38%
• Urethra	1	1.56%
• Gluteal region	5	7.81%
Morphology		
• Acetowhite-reactive lesion	16	25%
• Nodule	1	1.56%
• Plaque	16	25%
• Papule	2	3.13%
• Ulcer	4	6.25%
• Verrucous	27	42.19%
Coloration		
• Hyperpigmented	18	28.13%
• Hypochromic	6	9.38%
• Necrotic	2	3.13%
• Normal skin tone	39	60.94%
Symptomatology		
• Asymptomatic	49	76.56%
• Pain	2	3.13%
• Dyspareunia	0	-
• Pruritus	9	14.06%
• Vaginal discharge	4	6.25%

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DISCUSSION

The main objective of this study was to establish a clinical-epidemiological profile of patients with vulvar lesions treated at our hospital unit, allowing us to estimate the frequency and clinical characteristics of these pathologies. This is particularly relevant as there is a lack of literature in Mexico that aids in identifying risk factors and clinical manifestations in patients with vulvar lesions.

Various international studies have reported on the incidence of vulvar cancer, preceded by intraepithelial lesions of the vulva. The epidemiological risk factors that have been associated are age, infection with human papillomavirus (HPV), smoking, HIV infection, and lichen sclerosus (5,6). Studies from high-income countries have observed a significant increase in the incidence of vulvar cancer in women of reproductive age, smoking, immunosuppressive states (HIV), and transplant history (7,8).

Regarding the sociodemographic factors found in our unit, it is noteworthy that the most frequent age range was women of reproductive age, with an average of 38.57 years. This finding is similar to what has been reported in studies conducted in Latin American countries like Colombia, where the average age is 39.35 years (9). In terms of social factors, it was observed that most patients with vulvar lesions were married and had a basic education level. In contrast with the guidelines of the Spanish Association of Cervical Pathology and Colposcopy, which highlight smoking as a risk factor (10), in our study, 72.73% of patients reported not smoking. Another point of interest is sexual orientation. It was documented that 62 patients were heterosexual and only two were homosexual; however, this result may be influenced by biases, as sexual orientation is not always explored in medical histories or may be a taboo subject in our society. Regarding occupation, 46.97% of patients had a steady job and 43.94% were homemakers.

A relevant finding was the association between vulvar pathologies and immunosuppressive states, which has been described in literature from countries such as Germany, Colombia, and Spain (9,1,10). In our study, a significant percentage of patients with comorbidities causing immunosuppression (immune-mediated diseases, pregnancy, diabetes mellitus, transplant history, and immunosuppressive drug use) were identified. However, it is striking that only one patient was diagnosed with HIV.

The most common comorbidities among the patients in our unit were: chronic hypertension (23.44%), diabetes mellitus (17.19%), and chronic kidney disease (9.38%). Additionally, 10.94% had a history of cervical cancer, 26.56% had coexisting HPV infection in the cervix, and 20.31% had vulvar condylomatosis. Regarding factors that could represent immunocompromise, 12.50% had immune-related diseases, 3.13% had kidney transplant history, and 16.7% reported the use of immunosuppressants.

An effective strategy to reduce the incidence of vulvar cancer is the timely diagnosis and treatment of premalignant lesions, such as vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia, which is associated with persistent HPV infection (10). It has been reported that 80% of women with untreated high-grade vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia (VIN III) will develop invasive vulvar cancer (12).

The most common symptoms in vulvar pathology include a prolonged history of pruritus, accompanied by dysuria, discharge, and pain (13). However, in this study, 76.56% of patients were asymptomatic. Regarding clinical findings, most presented verrucous lesions and aceto-reactive lesions with coloration matching their skin tone, which differs from what is described in other literature. Due to this, diagnosis may be difficult, and timely treatment may be delayed.

This is highly relevant as, internationally, there has been an increase in the incidence of vulvar neoplasms, with a rate of 2.8 cases per 100,000 women. Additionally, GLOBOCAN reported in 2022 a prevalence of 2,257 cases in Latin America and the Caribbean, of which 355 correspond to Mexico in one year. The most common histological subtype of vulvar cancer is squamous cell carcinoma, previously considered a disease of postmenopausal women. However, in recent years, the average age of presentation has decreased, likely due to the increase in HPV infections (5), which may be treated or associated with comorbidities that cause immunosuppressive states, as well as the limited use of barrier methods during sexual intercourse in our unit.

CONCLUSION

Vulvar pathology remains an under-researched condition in Mexico. Internationally, an increasing incidence of vulvar cancer has been reported, largely secondary to precursor lesions such as vulvar intraepithelial neoplasia, which is predominantly associated with HPV infection. However, in Mexico, there are currently no established screening programs for early diagnosis.

Our study identified an epidemiological profile similar to that reported in international literature. Given that this condition is closely linked to HPV infection, its relevance is heightened by the fact that a significant proportion of our patients were of reproductive age, married, and lacked family planning methods. Furthermore, only a small percentage reported using barrier contraceptive methods, which may contribute to the increased prevalence of these infections.

For this reason, it is essential that healthcare services actively screen for vulvar lesions and perform biopsies on any detected vulvar abnormalities to facilitate the early identification of premalignant conditions. This is particularly crucial given that benign, inflammatory, infectious, premalignant, and malignant vulvar lesions can present with similar clinical features. Due to the rarity of this condition, failing to consider it in the differential diagnosis may lead to

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adverse outcomes for the patient. Establishing its epidemiological profile will contribute to improving screening strategies for at-risk patients.

Considering these findings, this study highlights the urgent need for dissemination and training strategies aimed at healthcare professionals regarding the clinical-epidemiological profile of patients with vulvar lesions in our population. Such initiatives will help promote targeted screening and timely management of this important health concern

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